

COESO

connecting research and society

COLLABORATIVE ENGAGEMENT ON SOCIETAL ISSUES

WP7 Communication and Dissemination

Communication and Dissemination Strategy

31 March 2021

Draft Version

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Deliverable 7.1
Communication and Dissemination Strategy

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1. Introduction

The [COESO project](#) (Collaborative Engagement on Societal Issues) is a 3-year participatory research project, funded by the European Commission through a *Science with and for Society* grant, and supported by the [OPERAS research infrastructure](#). This Communication and Dissemination strategic plan will guide the COESO consortium in its internal and external communication and dissemination actions.

The COESO project contributes to overcoming the obstacles that hinder the development of citizen science in the social sciences and humanities (SSH) and facilitates and supports participatory research through a service-first approach. The project will develop the Virtual Ecosystem for Research Activation (VERA), a collaborative place for knowledge production and sharing, and will collaborate with research funding organizations to enhance financial support for citizen science. At the heart of the project are ten citizen science pilots, representing a variety of social sciences and arts disciplines, societal challenges and types of engagement with citizens in different European countries. The five already built-in pilots address specific societal issues: mass tourism, education and gender, resilient societies, fight against crime, societal changes and migrations. COESO serves as a meeting point between various European communities: the social sciences and humanities community, the citizen science community, as well as the open scholarly communication community. As a bridging endeavour, COESO will take stock of existing communities such as [Hypotheses.org](#) and [EU-Citizen.Science](#). It will moreover explore the frontiers of innovation in the social sciences and humanities' public engagement through mutual learning and transmedia writing. Furthermore, to measure the quality of collaboration between researchers and citizens, COESO will design cooperation analytics.

The COESO Communication and Dissemination Strategy is developed in work package 7 (WP7) and serves as one of the pillars of the Project Exploitation and Dissemination Report (PEDR). The two areas of communication and dissemination do sometimes overlap but can be differentiated in the following way¹: Communication actions address various audiences to inform about the project, its results, and its overall goals. Communication actions are often dialogical and rely on engaging communities and receiving feedback. Dissemination activities focus on audiences that use the results in their own works to further enable the uptake and use of the project's results.

This document firstly describes the project's communication strategy, paying particular attention to its communication message, its targeted audiences and communication channels and activities. It also outlines COESO's visual identity and the timing of strategic actions. COESO works closely with the European research infrastructure OPERAS and has developed several measures that are to be shared between the two

¹ See: Executive Agency for Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (European Commission). "Making the most of your H2020 project: Boosting the impact of your project through effective communication, dissemination and exploitation." 2019. <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/3bb7278e-ebf3-11e9-9c4e-01aa75ed71a1/language-en/format-PDF/source-164620962>

consortia or coordinated conjointly. The chapter on COESO's communication strategy therefore describes these actions in detail and showcases the management of the communication strategy at large. The document secondly outlines the dissemination strategy, including targeted audiences, dissemination measures, and the timing of the action. Lastly, the communication and dissemination strategy describes the planned assessment of COESO's communication and dissemination measures.

Communication and dissemination responsibilities are transversally organized between EHESS-OpenEdition and MWS across all communication and dissemination channels. While MWS coordinates the communication and dissemination actions regarding the project's general aims and activities, EHESS-OpenEdition coordinates the communication and dissemination actions concerning the pilots and their activities. To ensure the workflow, both organizations have full access to the project's website and Twitter channel.

2. Communication

2.a Communication message

The main goals of the COESO communication strategy are to develop and strengthen a sustainable communication network, and to strengthen the communication messages both in terms of content and the way it is communicated. In addition to its communication messages, COESO seeks to communicate its mission, vision, and value proposition.

Communication messages. COESO will use the following communication messages that target different types of audiences (for more information on COESO’s target audiences, please read [2.b Target audiences](#)).

Audience	Communication message
General audience	Research and society meeting place
SSH researchers already involved in citizen science	“Collaboratory” for research and society
Societal actors already involved in citizen science	Research and society co-working place
Funding organizations for citizen science projects	Research with and for society
Policy makers at European, national, regional or local level	Research with and for society
SSH researchers who are not yet involved in citizen science	Connecting research and society
Societal actors who are not yet involved in citizen science	Connecting research and society
Researchers from other disciplines	Research with and for society
Research organizations and universities at large	Research and society co-working place
Service providers, such as libraries and infrastructure providers, etc.	Overcoming the obstacles that hinder the development of Citizen Science in the SSH
COESO consortium	“Collaboratory” for research and society
Members of the OPERAS research infrastructure	“Collaboratory” for research and society

Definition and mission. COESO aims to develop and sustain citizen science research in the SSH. COESO's mission is to enable strong growth of citizen science projects in the social sciences and humanities and to support participatory research through a service-first approach. The COESO project is an endeavour to bridge collaboration between the European social sciences and humanities community, the citizen science community, as well as the open scholarly communication community.

Vision. COESO's vision is to overcome the obstacles that hinder the development of citizen science in the social sciences and humanities.

Value proposition. Citizen science is a well-established domain in most of the scientific disciplines. Far less is known about the practices of citizen science in the SSH. These disciplines can be characterized by a diversity of publication languages, an entrenchment in diverse cultural backgrounds and the need for specific forms of scholarly communication (such as, amongst others, monographs, critical editions, and edited bibliographies). In addition, the small size of resource providers, the historical underfunding and lack of sustainability in this area, and the variety of technical skills and resources across the community lead to different practices of citizen science. Often under different names (such as e.g. public humanities), citizen science in the SSH involves intensive collaborations in small-scale projects. When developing citizen science practices, they therefore face specific challenges at different levels and lack the needed support.

COESO addresses these specific challenges that hinder the development of citizen science in the SSH by building a comprehensive framework that:

- hosts citizen science pilots reflecting the variety of citizen science practices and challenges in the SSH;
- supports them with collaborative tools through a specific virtual ecosystem (VERA);
- targets the funding streams needed to dramatically expand citizen science in the SSH;
- provides support and training to achieve public engagement in the SSH by mutual learning;
- produces knowledge on citizen science co-creation practices in the SSH through a rigorous assessment protocol on collaboration challenges in the pilots.

COESO's mission, vision, and value proposition aligns with that of OPERAS. OPERAS' mission is to coordinate and federate resources in Europe to efficiently address the scholarly communication needs of European researchers in the field of SSH. Its vision is to make Open Science a reality for research in the SSH and achieve a scholarly communication system where knowledge produced in the SSH benefits researchers, academics, students and, more generally, society across Europe and worldwide, without barriers.²

² See: <https://www.operas-eu.org/about/operas-in-a-nutshell/>

2.b Target audiences

COESO’s target audiences fall into different categories of stakeholders that are interested in the project and its goals. While this chapter defines these audiences, chapters [2.c Where do we communicate: communication channels](#) and [2.d Communication activities and events](#) describe how to reach them.

The primary target group is composed of SSH researchers and societal actors who are already involved in citizen science. COESO partners understand that the term “societal actors” can be misleading and links to a specific understanding of citizen science. Other terms to describe this audience of e.g. journalists, artists, independent stakeholders, small and medium-sized enterprises, non-commercial organizations, etc., are civil society, citizens, and socio-economic actors. While none of these terms speak to all audiences, we will use the term “societal actors” to describe the group of people outlined above. The secondary target audience is that of funding organizations for citizen science projects as well as policy makers on different levels, such as the European, national, regional or local one. A third target group is made up of SSH researchers and societal actors who are not yet involved in citizen science.

The last target audiences are researchers from other disciplines, research organizations and universities at large, as well as service providers, such as libraries and infrastructure providers, etc. While COESO’s communication is first and foremost targeted at audiences who are not members of the COESO consortium or members of the OPERAS research infrastructure, its communication actions always address both stakeholder groups. All targeted audiences can have more than one role, e.g. they can be an SSH researcher and at the same time part of the COESO consortium.

Img. 1. COESO’s target audiences

2.c Communication channels

COESO will use the following two main communication channels: a dedicated website including descriptive pages and a blog, as well as a Twitter channel. Both communication channels target a broad range of audiences and do not narrowly focus on only one group of stakeholders.

Project website

COESO's website has been created under the following domain: <https://coeso.hypotheses.org/>. Its presence on hypotheses.org, the platform for social sciences and humanities research blogs, ensures the involvement of an engaged audience at the very beginning of the project, a higher visibility and search engine optimization. It will feature the overall project information, as well as a blog, discussing current developments.

The overall project information on the website will include a brief project summary, highlighting the mission, vision and value proposition of the project. It will show the contents and the structure of the project, including the composition of the consortium and links to the public deliverables. On the blog, special attention will be paid to the pilots and their activities. The website including the blog will show information on events organized by the consortium, such as workshops and conferences, and external events where the project will have an active role (i.e. presentation of paper(s), organisation of sessions, stands with demos, etc.). COESO's website will also provide updates on the development of VERA.

The blog will be organized co-jointly by MWS and OpenEdition.

Multilingualism is particularly important for the social sciences and humanities and more so in the context of citizen science.³ The COESO blog will therefore be multilingual by allowing contributions in all European languages.

Blog posts are planned to be bundled into the following categories, which will be activated as soon as two blog posts that fall into the same category have been published:

- Pilots = Information on the pilots, their results, the open call.
- Citizen science & SSH = About concepts and topics of citizen science in the social sciences and humanities.
- What's up! = News on events and relevant dates.
- Mutual learning = About the mutual learning exercises and results developed mainly within the pilots.
- Funding citizen science = About funding options for citizen science in the social sciences and humanities and the COESO funding tool.
- Inside COESO = Information about the ongoing milestones and deliverables and

³ Read more on multilingualism in the SSH: <https://www.operas-eu.org/special-interest-groups/multilingualism/>

their achievements to make the project more approachable for people outside the consortium.

- Behind the Scenes = Information about the people involved in the project and in particular in the pilots. This category will be used to show how and why researchers and societal actors engage in citizen science.

To increase its overall visibility, the COESO communication team will pay special attention to optimize its website for the most common search engines, in particular Google. Pages on the website will be optimized for a maximum of three keywords each and be structured to align with best search engine optimization guidelines. This will be controlled with a tool for checking the keyword density as well as a tool for checking keyword optimization. All images will have a meta description and alt text. Page speed will be checked on a regular basis and, if too slow, measures, e.g. a reduction in image sizes, will be undertaken. The COESO communication team will constantly try to increase the Google indexation with its measures towards search engine optimization. The following communication items are a preliminary plan for the blog. They are subject to changes, deletions and further additions as the project evolves.

Date of the communication action	Coordinator of the action	Category	Content of the communication action
April 2021	MWS	Inside COESO	About COESO
April 2021	MWS	Citizen science & SSH	Concept of “societal actors”
May 2021	MWS	Citizen science & SSH	Concept of “collaboratory”
May 2021	MWS	Inside COESO	WP1: description of the work package
May 2021	OpenEdition	Pilots, What’s up	Pilot 3 - Focus Groups with involved citizens (information before the focus group)
June 2021	MWS	Inside COESO	What can OPERAS bring to COESO and how can COESO benefit from OPERAS
June 2021	MWS	Inside COESO	COESO advisory board
July 2021	OpenEdition	Pilots	Pilot 1: introduction to the pilot
July 2021	MWS	Funding citizen science	Landscape Study on Citizen Science Funding
July 2021	MWS	Behind the Scenes	Behind the Scenes: COESO coordinators
July 2021	OpenEdition	Pilots, What’s up	Pilot 3 - Focus Groups with involved citizens (information after the focus group)
August 2021	OpenEdition	Pilots	Pilot 5: introduction to the pilot
August 2021	MWS	Inside COESO	WP7: introduction to the work package
September 2021	OpenEdition	Pilots	Pilot 4: introduction to the pilot
September 2021	OpenEdition	Citizen science & SSH	PLACES project as proof of concept

October 2021	OpenEdition	Pilots	Pilot 2: introduction to the pilot
October 2021	MWS	Citizen science & SSH	Cooperation analytics: criteria grid and development
October 2021	MWS	Behind the Scenes	Behind the Scenes: communication officer
October 2021	OpenEdition	Pilots, What's up	Pilot 1 - First Workshop with local neighbourhoods (announcing the workshop)
November 2021	OpenEdition	Pilots	Pilot 3: introduction to the pilot
November 2021	MWS	Pilots	Open Call: announcing the Open Call
November 2021	OpenEdition	Pilots, What's up	First thematic school for pilots 1-5: announcing the thematic school
November 2021	OpenEdition	Mutual learning	Mutual learning exercise: Dance & Philosophy for Children
December 2021	OpenEdition	Behind the Scenes	Behind the Scenes: Pilot 1
December 2021	OpenEdition	Inside COESO, Pilots	WP2: description of the work package
December 2021	OpenEdition	Pilots, What's up	Pilot 1 - First Workshop with local neighbourhoods (report of the workshop)
January 2022	OpenEdition	Behind the Scenes	Behind the Scenes: Pilot 3
January 2022	MWS	Inside COESO	WP4: introduction to the work package
January 2022	OpenEdition	Pilots, what's up	First thematic school for pilots 1-5: report of the thematic school
January 2022	OpenEdition	Mutual learning	Mutual learning exercise: Almadanza
February 2022	OpenEdition	Behind the Scenes	Behind the Scenes: Pilot 2
February 2022	MWS	Pilots	Open Call: announcing selection of pilots
February 2022	MWS	Citizen science & SSH	Interview with the project officer Colombe Warin about citizen science in Europe
February 2022	MWS	Inside COESO	VERA - general description
March 2022	OpenEdition	Behind the Scenes	Behind the Scenes: Pilot 4
March 2022	MWS	Inside COESO	WP5: description of the work package
March 2022	OpenEdition	Pilots	Podcast 1 (about Pilot 1)
March 2022	OpenEdition	Pilots	Cafébabel multimedia article 1 (about Pilot 1)
Spring (April-June) 2022	OpenEdition	Mutual learning	Mutual learning exercise: Institut Choréographique International
April 2022	OpenEdition	Pilots	Pilot 3: report on the technical and legal framework for sharing confidential data
April 2022	OpenEdition	Pilots	Pilot 3: report on accessibility to sensitive and privately-owned databases

April 2022	OpenEdition	Pilots	Podcast 2 (about Pilot 3)
April 2022	OpenEdition	Pilots, What's up	Pilot 1 - Second Workshop with local neighbourhoods (announcing the workshop)
May 2022	OpenEdition	Pilots	Pilot 2 - MemoRekall capsule
May 2022	OpenEdition	Behind the Scenes	Behind the Scenes: Pilot 5
May 2022	MWS	Inside COESO	Podcast 3 (about VERA)
June 2022	MWS	Inside COESO	WP3: description of the work package
June 2022	MWS	Behind the Scenes	Behind the Scenes: EU project officer
June 2022	OpenEdition	Pilots	Podcast 4 (about Pilot 2)
June 2022	OpenEdition	Pilots	Cafébabel multimedia article 2 (about Pilot 2)
June 2022	OpenEdition	Pilots, What's up	Pilot 1 - Second Workshop with local neighbourhoods (report of the workshop)
July 2022	MWS	What's up, Inside COESO	COESO consortium meeting (halfway validation workshop)
July 2022	MWS	Pilots	Pilot 1: Transmedia website on the LTO engagement in the urban space
July 2022	MWS	Citizen science & SSH	Report on test and final development of the Cooperation Analytics
July 2022	OpenEdition	Citizen science & SSH	Policy brief 1
July 2022	OpenEdition	Pilots	Pilot 2: choreographic score
July 2022	OpenEdition	Pilots	Pilot 2: paper on gender issues related to desire and body awareness
July 2022	OpenEdition	Pilots	Pilot 3: solution journalism outputs
July 2022	MWS	What's up, funding citizen science	Funding Advocacy Workshop with funding stakeholders: announcing the workshop
July 2022	OpenEdition	Pilots	Podcast 5 (about Pilot 4)
July 2022	OpenEdition	Pilots	Cafébabel multimedia article 3 (about Pilot 4)
August 2022	MWS	Inside COESO	WP8: introduction to the work package
August 2022	MWS	Funding citizen science	Advocacy for SSH funding
before Summer-Autumn 2022	OpenEdition	Pilots, What's up	Pilot 5 - Symposium (information before the symposium)
September 2022	MWS	What's up, Inside COESO	COESO review meeting in Brussels
September 2022	MWS	What's up, Funding citizen science	Funding Advocacy Workshop with funding stakeholders: report of the workshop
September 2022	OpenEdition	Pilots, What's up	Second thematic school for pilots 6-10: announcing the thematic school

September 2022	OpenEdition	Pilots	Podcast 6 (about Pilot 5)
after Summer-Autumn 2022	OpenEdition	Pilots, What's up	Pilot 5 - Symposium (report of the symposium)
October 2022	OpenEdition	Pilots, Inside COESO	Expected impact of COESO (based on the impact of the pilots)
October 2022	OpenEdition	Pilots	Pilot 6: introduction to the pilot
October 2022	MWS	Funding citizen science	Podcast 7 (for funding institutions)
November 2022	MWS	Inside COESO	WP6: introduction to the work package
November 2022	OpenEdition	Pilots, what's up	Second thematic school for pilots 6-10: report on the thematic school
November 2022	OpenEdition	Pilots	Pilot 7: introduction to the pilot
November 2022	MWS	Funding citizen science	Podcast 8 (for funding institutions)
December 2022	OpenEdition	Mutual learning	Mutual learning exercise: Babel Academy
December 2022	OpenEdition	Pilots	Pilot 8: introduction to the pilot
December 2022	MWS	Funding citizen science	Podcast 9 (for funding institutions)
January 2023	OpenEdition	Pilots	Pilot 1: Final Report
January 2023	OpenEdition	Pilots	Pilot 5: Writing Across Borders" outputs
January 2023	MWS	Inside COESO	VERA dashboard (beta version)
February 2023	MWS	Inside COESO	EU-Citizen.science connector
February 2023	OpenEdition	Pilots	Pilot 9: introduction to the pilot
March 2023	OpenEdition	Pilots	Pilot 10: introduction to the pilot
March 2023	OpenEdition	Behind the Scenes	Behind the Scenes: Pilot 6
March 2023	MWS	Inside COESO	TRIPLE and COESO (goTriple and VERA)
April 2023	OpenEdition	Behind the Scenes	Behind the Scenes: Pilot 7
April 2023	MWS	Citizen science & SSH	Citizen science in the SSH: specific challenges
May 2023	MWS	What's up, funding citizen science	Funding Advocacy Workshop with funding tool users: announcing the workshop
May 2023	OpenEdition	Behind the Scenes	Behind the Scenes: Pilot 8
May 2023	OpenEdition	Pilots, what's up	Third thematic school: announcing the thematic school
June 2023	OpenEdition	Behind the Scenes	Behind the Scenes: Pilot 9

July 2023	MWS	Inside COESO	VERA widget
July 2023	OpenEdition	Pilots, What's up	Third thematic school: report on the thematic school
July 2023	MWS	What's up, Funding citizen science	Funding Advocacy Workshop with funding tool users: report on the workshop
August 2023	OpenEdition	Behind the Scenes	Behind the Scenes: Pilot 10
September 2023	OpenEdition	Pilots	Report on activism and science within citizen science
September 2023	MWS	Inside COESO	WP6: report on its activities
September 2023	MWS	What's up	COESO final conference: information, invitation and registration
November 2023	OpenEdition	Citizen science & SSH	Policy brief 2
November 2023	MWS	Behind the Scenes	Behind the Scenes: VERA developers
December 2023	MWS	What's up, Inside COESO	COESO final conference: report on the conference
December 2023	MWS	Citizen science & SSH	Report on SSH contribution to citizen science
December 2023	MWS	Inside COESO	COESO's exploitation strategy
December 2023	MWS	Inside COESO	"Goodbye"

Social media

COESO has created its own dedicated Twitter channel (@COESOEU) to increase the reach and visibility of the activities and of VERA. In addition to the Twitter channel, the already active channels of the OPERAS RI (Twitter: @OPERASEU, LinkedIn: @OPERASEU, Facebook: @OPERASEU) will be used (see more on the communication synergies between COESO and OPERAS in [2.g Shared communication measures between COESO and OPERAS](#)). As social media is typically a conversational channel, the whole COESO consortium will be invited to take an active part in the conversations. COESO organizes its content on Twitter by categorizing the tweets in the following categories (more might be added over time):

[#COESO] = for project news and results, including information about the ongoing milestones and deliverables, and information about the people involved in the project.

[#meetCOESO] = for announcements and news about events planned or attended by the COESO consortium

[#OPERAS] = communication on OPERAS activities

[#CitizenScience] = for news from the community, including concepts and topics of citizen science in the social sciences and funding options

- [#tourismobservatory] = Pilot 1
- [#dancingphilosophy] = Pilot 2
- [#solutionsjournalism] = Pilot 3
- [#sensitivedatasharing] = Pilot 4
- [#migrantknowledge] = Pilot 5

COESO will use the same hashtag for all events it organizes: #meetCOESO. All events that are organized within COESO might use a second hashtag.

In addition to tweeting about the communication actions on the blog and reacting to news from the community, the following preliminary tweet series are planned to increase attention. They are subject to change as the project evolves.

Date	Coordinator	Category	Content
April 2021	MWS	[#COESO]	About COESO - 1 tweet each week about the project's mission, vision, value proposition, and work packages over 3 months
May 2021	MWS	[#COESO]	Project partners - 1 tweet on each consortium partner
June 2021	MWS	[#OPERAS]	OPERAS: what it is - 10 tweets
June 2021	MWS	[#COESO]	COESO advisory board - 1 tweet for each member
July 2021	MWS	[#CitizenScience]	Landscape Study on Citizen Science Funding - 10 tweets with interesting findings from the study
July 2021	OpenEdition	[#tourismobservatory]	Pilot 1 - 10 tweets
August 2021	OpenEdition	[#migrantknowledge]	Pilot 5 - 10 tweets
September 2021	OpenEdition	[#sensitivedatasharing]	Pilot 4 - 10 tweets
September 2021	MWS	[#COESO]	COESO communication messages - 1 tweet for each message
October 2021	OpenEdition	[#dancingphilosophy]	Pilot 2 - 10 tweets
November 2021	OpenEdition	[#solutionsjournalism]	Pilot 3 - 10 tweets
November 2021	OpenEdition	Mutual learning	Mutual learning exercise: Dance & Philosophy for Children - 5 tweets
November 2021 - January 2022	OpenEdition	[#meetCOESO]	Thematic School 1: Pilot 1-5 - 1 tweet per pilot
November 2021 - February 2022	OpenEdition	[#COESO]	Open Call - 2 tweets per week during launch of Open Call
December 2021	MWS	[#OPERAS]	OPERAS: how to engage - 10 tweet

January 2022	MWS	[#CitizenScience]	Funding Advocacy - 10 tweets with recommendations from the Advocacy Action Plan
January 2022	OpenEdition	Mutual learning	Mutual learning exercise: Almadanza - 5 tweets
March 2022	OpenEdition	[#tourismobservatory]	Podcast 1 (about Pilot 1) - 5 tweets
March 2022	OpenEdition	[#tourismobservatory]	Cafébabel multimedia article 1 (about Pilot 1)
April 2022	OpenEdition	[#solutionsjournalism]	Podcast 2 (about Pilot 3) - 5 tweets
Spring (between April-June) 2022	OpenEdition	Mutual learning	Mutual learning exercise: Institut Choréographique International - 5 tweets
June 2022	OpenEdition	[#dancingphilosophy]	Podcast 4 (about Pilot 2) - 5 tweets
June 2022	OpenEdition	[#dancingphilosophy]	Cafébabel multimedia article 2 (about Pilot 2) - 5 tweets
July 2022	MWS	[#CitizenScience]	Policy brief 1 - 10 tweets
July 2022	MWS	[#COESO]	Cooperation analytics - 5 tweets
July 2022	OpenEdition	[#sensitivedatasharing]	Podcast 5 (about Pilot 4) - 5 tweets
July 2022	OpenEdition	[#sensitivedatasharing]	Cafébabel multimedia article 3 (about Pilot 4) - 5 tweets
July - September 2022	MWS	[#meetCOESO]	Funding Advocacy Workshop with funding stakeholders - 10 tweets on agenda and 10 tweets with results
September 2022	OpenEdition	[#migrantknowledge]	Podcast 6 (about Pilot 5) - 5 tweets
September - November 2022	OpenEdition	[#meetCOESO]	Thematic School 2: Pilot 6-10 - 1 tweet per pilot
October 2022	OpenEdition	tbc	Pilot 6 - 10 tweets
October 2022	MWS	[#COESO]	Expected impact of COESO - 5 tweets
October 2022	MWS	[#COESO]	Podcast 7 (for funding institutions) - 5 tweets
November 2022	OpenEdition	tbc	Pilot 7 - 10 tweets
November 2022	MWS	[#COESO]	Podcast 8 (for funding institutions) - 5 tweets
December 2022	OpenEdition	tbc	Pilot 8 - 10 tweets
December 2022	MWS	[#COESO]	Podcast 9 (for funding institutions) - 5 tweets
February 2023	OpenEdition	tbc	Pilot 9 - 10 tweets
February 2023	MWS	[#COESO]	EU-Citizen.Science connector - 5 tweets

March 2023	OpenEdition	tbc	Pilot 10 - 10 tweets
March	MWS	[#COESO]	goTriple & VERA - 5 tweets
April 2023	MWS	[#CitizenScience]	citizen science in the SSH: specific challenges - 10 tweets
April 2023	MWS	[#COESO]	VERA - one tweet per “function” of VERA
May - July 2023	OpenEdition	[#meetCOESO]	Thematic School 3 - 1 tweet per pilot
May - July 2023		[#meetCOESO]	Funding Advocacy Workshop with funding tool users - 10 tweets about agenda and 10 tweets about results
July 2023	MWS	[#COESO]	VERA widget - 5 tweets
September 2023	MWS	[#CitizenScience]	Activism and science within citizen science - 10 tweets with findings from the study
September - December 2023	MWS	[#meetCOESO]	COESO final conference - tweets will be chosen depending on the programme
November 2023	MWS	[#CitizenScience]	Policy brief 2 - 10 tweets
December 2023	MWS	[#CitizenScience]	SSH contribution to citizen science - 10 tweets with findings from the report

In addition to the external communication channels, COESO uses the following project internal communication channels to organize its work and to reach its project partners:

- A general project partner mailing list
- Mailing lists for each work package
- Dedicated Mattermost chat channels

All COESO meetings are open to all project partners and all documentation is openly accessible.

A template for deliverables and publications will be provided (see more details in the chapter on [Dissemination](#)).

2.d Communication activities and events

COESO follows a proactive strategy to communicate its communication message and content. Apart from the website and social media, its main communication actions are: a podcast series; an article series; the organization of a final conference and of two workshops; the provision of content for several European newsletters; the production of two policy briefs; and the presentation of the projects, its communication messages, and the VERA platform, on relevant events. The diversity of these measures will ensure that a broad audience of people with different backgrounds can be reached.

Podcast series

COESO will develop a regular podcast series, which will be mainly used to showcase the work that has been done in the Pilots. Bulle Media, in cooperation with Cafébabel, will produce nine podcasts. Five podcasts will be about the Pilots, e.g. with a societal actor, a researcher, or someone from the COESO consortium. One podcast will be about the VERA platform and three podcasts will be about the funding perspective and will most probably include interviews with funders. As the goal of the podcasts is to tell a story, they will have a maximum length of 10-12 minutes in order to hold the attention of listeners. All podcasts will be produced in English and promoted through Europod. They will be available on popular streaming platforms to engage a broad audience.

The tentative dissemination plan of the podcasts is as follows:

- March 2022 = M15: podcast about pilot 1
- April 2022 = M16: podcast about pilot 3
- May 2022 = M17: podcast about VERA platform
- June 2022 = M18: podcast about pilot 2
- July 2022 = M19: podcast about pilot 4
- September 2022 = M21: podcast about pilot 5
- October 2022 = M22: podcast for institutions
- November 2022 = M23: podcast for institutions
- December 2022 = M24: podcast for institutions

Articles series

COESO will produce three original multimedia articles, focusing on the following three pilots:

- March 2022 = M15: pilot 1
- June 2022 = M18: pilot 2
- July 2022 = M19: pilot 4

Cafébabel will write these articles in French and they will be translated in English, Spanish, Italian, German, and Polish, summing up to 18 articles in total. The production plan is coordinated with the podcasts produced by Bulle Media, e.g. by adding the podcast widget to the articles to thus increase the audience reach and impact.

Final Conference

A final, research-driven conference, addressing the SSH community as well as socio-economic actors, will be organized towards the end of the project. The minimum number of attendees is planned to be 80. The event will take place on-site at Campus Condorcet in Paris, France. An open discussion on a hybrid and other solutions of the conference will take place.

Workshops on funding

Two workshops will be organized to open the funding tool to new funding opportunities. The first workshop will be directed at funding stakeholders to discuss their needs, inclusion and possible development of Citizen Science grants in the funding tool. This workshop will take place in August 2022 and will be organized by Ibercivis/ECSA and CNRS-CNE. The second one towards the end of the project, planned for June 2023, will be directed at future users of the tool to test its application against community needs.

It will be organized by RFIEA and EHESS-OE. The target number of attendees for each workshop is 30 people.

Newsletter

In order to reach a broader and more diverse audience, COESO will integrate its content into the OPERAS newsletter (see: <https://www.operas-eu.org/operas-newsletter>). The OPERAS newsletter currently has 220 subscribers and is disseminated four times a year. In addition, COESO will integrate its newsletter content into the EU-Citizen.Science newsletter (see: <https://us20.campaign-archive.com/home/?u=43994d556fa8e50df2ec2c705&id=dd5b2f8cb2>), which includes news from a variety of citizen science projects in Europe and is disseminated three times per year. COESO encourages its consortium members to also include its news into their institutional newsletters.

Policy briefs

COESO will write at least two policy briefs. They are planned to be communicated in July 2022 and November 2023 respectively. The two policy briefs will contain suggestions on policy implementations on the topic of SSH and the practices of citizen science, as well as the topic of citizen science funding in the SSH.

Conferences, workshops, and other events

The COESO consortium is very much aware of the need to actively promote and engage with future users of VERA at workshops, fairs, and congresses in Europe and beyond to develop a sustainable community of users. Therefore, the COESO communication officer will identify those events over the course of COESO where at least one COESO partner will attend and/or present the project. In order to receive feedback from the consortium partners, the following question has been added to the model of the rolling minutes of each WP:

- *Have you presented COESO at any event since the last meeting?*
- *Do you already have plans to present COESO at a scheduled event?*

A strategic and open calendar listing relevant events and keeping track of COESO consortium members' participation can be found here: <https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1bviP4ArYcyU1utzFVPZDike1LmKPB1zjCHwoLkKHwql/edit#gid=1476603722>

2.e Visual identity

The visual identity for the project is further described on Deliverable 7.2 “Dissemination Materials Guide”. The overall COESO visual system will include a logo and its variations, a favicon, a banner, graphical elements and style guidelines for online and offline publications and dissemination material. The different elements will be made accessible to all project partners and will be created in an open format to enable easy adaption of the files.

2.g Shared communication measures between COESO and OPERAS

OPERAS and COESO will share some communication measures and support each other with relevant communication actions. This ensures that COESO's communication actions will reach a broader audience and OPERAS' communication actions profit from knowledge on citizen science and an active community. Both, OPERAS and COESO communication teams, are coordinated by MWS to ensure a regular and targeted communication on the shared communication measures. OPERAS will also play an important role in the exploitation of COESO's results (see more in the upcoming PEDR).

COESO website and blog

The COESO website and blog will visibly link to the OPERAS website and blog. It will have a dedicated page on OPERAS that can be found in the menu.

OPERAS website

There will be a dedicated page about COESO to be found in the menu under "projects" (<https://www.operas-eu.org/projects/>) with information about the project and a link to the COESO website. OPERAS currently lists the COESO service as "Research for Society Service" (see <https://www.operas-eu.org/services/research-for-society/>).

OPERAS blog

COESO will keep its own blog but will make use of the OPERAS blog (<https://operas.hypotheses.org/>) as well. Certain types of blog posts, including "Behind the Scenes" with COESO partners, posts on the VERA platform, and event announcements will be posted on and adapted for the OPERAS blog.

COESO Twitter

COESO will develop a tweet series that focuses on OPERAS, particularly its activities with a strong link to COESO. These include TRIPLE, the OPERAS Special Interest Group on tools, the OPERAS Special Interest Group on COESO, as well as the CO-OPERAS IN.

OPERAS social media channels

OPERAS will post information about COESO, especially its blog posts and events, on its Twitter (<https://twitter.com/OPERASEU>), Facebook (https://de-de.facebook.com/pg/OPERASEU/community/?ref=page_internal), and LinkedIn (<https://de.linkedin.com/company/operas>) channel.

COESO will develop a tweet series to be used on the OPERAS social media channels after one year and towards the end of the project. All tweets related to COESO can be identified by [#COESO].

OPERAS newsletter

COESO will not keep a newsletter but rather include its news into the already existing OPERAS newsletter. To that end, the COESO communication officer sends her news to the OPERAS communication officer before each newsletter publication.

Topics within OPERAS that are of interest to the COESO community

There are a range of topics, initiatives, special interest groups, and projects within the OPERAS community that are of particular interest to the COESO community. These include the following:

- [CO-OPERAS](#): How should data be saved to be FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable) and how can it be stored on the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)? COESO will work with the FAIR criteria to store their research data.
- [TRIPLE](#): TRIPLE, an innovative multilingual and multicultural discovery solution for the SSH, will provide a single access point that allows to explore, find, access and reuse materials such as literature, data, projects and researcher profiles at European scale. COESO will cooperate with the TRIPLE project for a crowdfunding solution.
- [OPERAS Special Interest Group Tools Research and Development](#): This Special Interest Group is of interest to the development of VERA.
- [OPERAS Advocacy Special Interest Group](#): This Special Interest Group is of interest to COESO's activities on citizen science funding.

3. Dissemination

3.a Strategy

For an effective and efficient dissemination of the project's results, the dissemination plan is linked strongly with the communication plan. The dissemination plan first defines the target audiences (within and outside of the project's consortium) that COESO wishes to reach. The plan then defines different dissemination measures. This is then brought together in a target audience-dissemination measure-matrix to identify which dissemination measure is particularly suited for which audience. Finally, it gives information on the timing of the dissemination measures.

3.b Target audiences

COESO's dissemination strategy targets those audiences that are interested in the results of the project instead of the project and its goals as such.

The target audiences are very similar to the ones of the communication actions and, as with the targeted communication stakeholders, all audiences for COESO's dissemination measures can fall into more than one of the categories described. The primary target group is composed of SSH researchers and societal actors who are already involved in citizen science. This includes, for example, journalists, artists and other independent stakeholders, small and medium enterprises, and non-profit organizations. The secondary target audience is that of funding organizations for citizen science projects as well as policy makers on different levels, such as the European, national, regional or local one. The third target audience is made up of SSH researchers and societal actors who are not yet involved in citizen science. The last target audiences are researchers from other disciplines, research organizations and universities at large, as well as service providers, such as libraries and infrastructure providers, etc. In addition, dissemination measures also target other SwafS related projects and the COESO and OPERAS consortium.

3.c Dissemination measures

The project's results will be disseminated via the communication channels that are identified in [2.c Communication channels](#). Dissemination measures include scientific publications, reports on COESO-initiated events such as conferences and workshops, reports on events that the COESO consortium participates in and presents the project at, training and guideline materials, advocacy material, as well as the project deliverables.

All dissemination measures (unless specifically stated otherwise, as e.g. in the case of some deliverables) will be public and open access. COESO uses the OPERAS community ("OPERAS: open scholarly communication in the european research area for social

sciences and humanities”: <https://zenodo.org/communities/operaseu/?page=1&size=20>) on Zenodo to upload all COESO publications and deliverables. In addition, COESO’s publications will be linked to other “citizen science in the SSH” communities on Zenodo that fit their content, in particular but not exclusively the following:

- “Citizen Science”: <https://zenodo.org/communities/citizenscience/?page=1&size=20> (not linked to a specific project)
- “Open Citizen Social Science”: <https://zenodo.org/communities/opencitizensocialscience/?page=1&size=20> (linked to the [CoAct](#) project but open to resources from other projects)

3.d Target groups - dissemination measure - plan

Target audience		Dissemination measures				
		<i>Publications</i>	<i>Reports on COESO events</i>	<i>Trainings, guidelines, reports</i>	<i>Online dissemination</i>	<i>Project deliverables</i>
<i>Researchers</i>	<i>SSH researchers</i>	Pilot articles, Pilot research papers, COESO research papers	Workshop for future users of the funding tool, Pilot events, Final Conference	Open Call, Landscape study on Citizen Science funding	Pilot blogs, social media, podcasts, articles in Cafébabel	Report on accessibility to sensitive and privately-owned databases, Report on SSH contribution to Citizen Science, Report on ethical thinking in Citizen Science, Report on activism and science within Citizen Science
	<i>Researchers from other disciplines</i>	Pilot articles, Pilot research papers, COESO research papers	Workshop for future users of the funding tool, Pilot events,	Open Call, Landscape study on Citizen Science funding,	Pilot blogs, social media, podcasts, articles in Cafébabel	Report on accessibility to sensitive and privately-owned databases, Report on ethical thinking in Citizen Science, Report on activism and science within Citizen Science
<i>Societal actors</i>	<i>Journalists</i>	Pilot articles	Workshop for future users of the funding tool, Pilot events, Final Conference	Open Call, Landscape study on Citizen Science funding,	Pilot blogs, social media, podcasts, articles in Cafébabel	Report on accessibility to sensitive and privately-owned databases, Report on SSH contribution to Citizen Science, Report on ethical thinking in Citizen Science, Report on activism and science within Citizen Science
	<i>Artists and other independent professionals</i>	Pilot articles	Workshop for future users of the funding tool, Pilot events,	Open Call, Landscape study on Citizen Science funding,	Pilot blogs, social media, podcasts, articles in Cafébabel	Report on SSH contribution to Citizen Science, Report on ethical thinking in Citizen Science, Report on activism and science within Citizen Science
	<i>Small and medium enterprises</i>	Pilot research papers	Workshop for future users of the funding tool, Pilot events,	Open Call, Landscape study on Citizen Science funding,	articles in Cafébabel	Report on accessibility to sensitive and privately-owned databases, Report on SSH contribution to Citizen Science, Report on ethical thinking in Citizen Science

	<i>Non-profit organizations</i>	Pilot research papers	Workshop for future users of the funding tool, Pilot events,	Open Call, Landscape study on Citizen Science funding,	social media, podcasts, articles in Cafébabel	Report on accessibility to sensitive and privately-owned databases, Report on SSH contribution to Citizen Science, Report on ethical thinking in Citizen Science, Report on activism and science within Citizen Science
	<i>Other interested societal actors</i>	Pilot articles, Pilot research papers	Workshop for future users of the funding tool, Pilot events,	Open Call, Landscape study on Citizen Science funding,	Pilot blogs, social media, podcasts, articles in Cafébabel	Report on accessibility to sensitive and privately-owned databases, Report on SSH contribution to Citizen Science, Report on ethical thinking in Citizen Science, Report on activism and science within Citizen Science
	<i>Funding organizations</i>	COESO research papers	Workshop for funding stakeholders , Final Conference	Open Call, Landscape study on Citizen Science funding	project website,	Report on SSH contribution to Citizen Science, Report on ethical thinking in Citizen Science
	<i>Policy makers</i>	COESO research papers	Workshop for future users of the funding tool, Workshop for funding stakeholders , Final Conference	Landscape study on Citizen Science funding, Funding Advocacy Action Plan	project website	Report on SSH contribution to Citizen Science, Report on ethical thinking in Citizen Science, Report on activism and science within Citizen Science
	<i>Research organizations and universities</i>	COESO research papers	Workshop for future users of the funding tool, Workshop for funding stakeholders , Final Conference	Open Call, Landscape study on Citizen Science funding	project website, articles in Cafébabel	Report on accessibility to sensitive and privately-owned databases, Report on SSH contribution to Citizen Science, Report on ethical thinking in Citizen Science, Report on activism and science within Citizen Science
	<i>Service providers (e.g. scientific publishers and libraries)</i>	COESO research papers	Workshop for future users of the funding tool, Workshop for funding stakeholders , Final Conference		project website, articles in Cafébabel	Report on test and final development, Report on SSH contribution to Citizen Science, Report on activism and science within Citizen Science
	<i>SwafS related projects</i>	Pilot research papers, COESO research papers	Workshop for future users of the funding tool, Workshop for funding stakeholders , Pilot events, Final Conference	Open Call, Landscape study on Citizen Science funding, Funding Advocacy Action Plan	project website, social media, specific mailing to related projects representatives (e.g. newsletters released specifically for related projects), cross posting of announcements	Report on accessibility to sensitive and privately-owned databases, Report on SSH contribution to Citizen Science, Report on ethical thinking in Citizen Science, Report on activism and science within Citizen Science

<i>COESO and OPERAS Consortium</i>	Pilot research papers, COESO research papers	Workshop for future users of the funding tool, Workshop for funding stakeholders, Pilot events, Final Conference	Open Call, Landscape study on Citizen Science funding, Funding Advocacy Action Plan	project website, social media, podcasts, articles in Cafébabel	Report on accessibility to sensitive and privately-owned databases, Report on test and final development, Report on SSH contribution to Citizen Science, Report on ethical thinking in Citizen Science, Report on activism and science within Citizen Science
<i>General public</i>	Project news items, Pilots announcements	Final conference	Landscape study on Citizen Science funding	project website, social media, press releases	Report on activism and science within Citizen Science

3.e Timing

In order to efficiently and effectively time the dissemination measures during the project, a calendar outlining the timing of those measures has been developed. It plans all dissemination activities according to the project’s development; thus, in the beginning the dissemination material will mostly focus on what the project wants to achieve and during the course of the project, these measures will become more detailed and concrete. The timing of the dissemination measures are closely linked to the communication actions developed in [2.d Communication activities and events](#) to ensure a broad dissemination of the various project outputs.

For the timing of the blog posts, social media series, podcasts, and articles in Cafébabel, please refer to the respective chapters in the section on the Communication measures. The table below focuses on publications, reports on COESO events, training material, guidelines. All of them are public project deliverables.

Planned publication date	Coordinator	Dissemination output
March 2021	MWS	D7.1 Communication and Dissemination Strategy
June 2021	MWS	D1.1 DMP and updates
June 2021	MWS	D4.1 Landscape Study on Citizen Science Funding
June 2021	MWS	D7.7 PEDR
October 2021	MWS	D4.3 Funding Advocacy Action Plan
November 2021	MWS	D2.1 Open Call texts and rules
March 2022	OpenEdition	D2.9 Report on the technical and legal framework for sharing confidential data
March 2022	OpenEdition	D2.8 Report on accessibility to sensitive and privately-owned databases
June 2022	OpenEdition	D1.4 Policy brief 1

June 2022	OpenEdition	D2.6 Paper on gender issues related to desire and body awareness
June 2022	MWS	D5.2 Report on test and final development of the Cooperation Analytics
December 2022	OpenEdition	D2.3 Lisbon Tourism Observatory Final Report
August 2023	OpenEdition	D5.3 Report on activism and science within citizen science
August 2023	MWS	D6.1 Report on the activities of WP6
October 2023	OpenEdition	D1.5 Policy brief 2
December 2023	MWS	D7.6 Report on SSH contribution to citizen science
December 2023	MWS	D7.5 Report on Dissemination Activities

4. Assessment of the Communication and Dissemination Measures

The progress of the communication and dissemination activities will be monitored constantly by making use of analytics, in particular of the project website and the social media, and will be adjusted accordingly. In addition, regular evaluation meetings between the project management team and the communication team will give an opportunity to discuss the strengths and weaknesses of the communication and dissemination process and to adapt it.

The communication and dissemination strategy will be re-evaluated as part of the following documents:

- M6: Draft PEDR
- M18: Draft Report on Dissemination Activities
- M30: Final PEDR
- M36: Final Report on Dissemination Activities

Finally, success indicators will be used to obtain different feedback (KPIs). KPIs measure the effect of dissemination strategies and they evaluate the success of communication activities. The first step will be to choose the right KPIs for each activity. For example, the number of users of the COESO blogs, as well as the number of inquiries received and the responses to publications, e.g. on Zenodo, will be taken into account to evaluate interest. In the case of oral communication channels, like a workshop, the KPIs will be, among others, the audience attending the event, their feedback, and their participation in future events. Most of the KPIs will be measured thanks to surveys, especially concerning the oral communication channels. But the consortium also plans to use technical tools of measurement that are useful for online communication. Those tools will be defined in the PEDR.